

Effects of *Trichoderma asperellum* and arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi on *Dombeya torrida* growth and biocontrol against *Armillaria* species

Alex Machio Kange^{*1}, Philip Cheruiyot Sitienei²

¹Department of Agriculture and Natural Resources, Bomet University College, Bomet, Kenya

²Department of Biological Sciences, Egerton University, Egerton, Kenya

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Abstract

Armillaria root rot disease caused by *Armillaria* species is one the most widespread and important disease of many forest trees. An interaction between arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) and *Trichoderma asperellum* have beneficial effects on plant growth as well as to the host plants and may affect plant resistance. The objective of this study was to determine the ability of *T. asperellum* to promote plant growth and reduce *Armillaria* root rot disease in green house condition. *Armillaria* species was isolated from a severely infected *Dombeya torrida* plant and cultured on malt extract agar. Each plant was inoculated by placing four mycelial agar plugs cut-out from a 14-days old *Armillaria* species after every one month of plant growth. The inoculations of *T. asperellum* were done at 0 day of the experiment then repeated at an interval of 30 days up to the 150 days while AMF was inoculated once at the onset of the experiment. Plants that were co-inoculated with *T. asperellum* and AMF exhibited the highest fresh weights and plant height. The presence of *T. asperellum* increased AMF root colonization compared to plants inoculated with the AMF. The fungal interaction revealed a negative interference between AMF and *T. asperellum* on root colonization of *D. torrida* seedlings. This demonstrated that inoculation of AMF and *T. asperellum* either individually or in combination enhanced plant growth response of *D. torrida* seedlings.

*Corresponding Author: Alex Machio Kange ✉ machiopj@gmail.com

Introduction

Armillaria species are widely associated with woody plant taxa as pathogens, wood decay agents and even as mutualists with orchids (Baumgartner *et al.*, 2011; Mihail, 2013). Members of the fungal genus *Armillaria* species occur in boreal, temperate and tropical forests worldwide, and *Armillaria* root disease (ARD) is known to occur on all continents except Antarctica (Westwood *et al.*, 2012). The *Armillaria* fungi, which are feared by foresters, belong to an important and cosmopolitan pathogens inside and outside the forest. They can attack almost all species of hardwoods and coniferous of all ages (Gibbs *et al.*, 2002). *Armillaria* root disease is a common disease of both forest and agricultural crops. More than 30 *Armillaria* species exist world-wide (Cruickshank *et al.*, 2011). The ARD is mostly present in many forest regions of Canada, affecting over 200 million hectares (Canadian Forest Service, 2010). Kenya has 3.47 million hectares of forest cover FAO (2010): The ARD is an important contributor to tree mortality in the forests and has resulted in loss of forest cover thus a significant economic losses (Bendel and Rigling, 2008). Besides, in forests the *Armillaria* are important root rot pathogens of tea (*Camellia sinensis* L. O. Kuntze) in the highland areas (altitude >1500 m above the sea level (a.s.l.)) of Kenya (Otieno *et al.*, 2003_b). *Armillaria* species can survive in the soil, on wood and root debris in the absence of any living host and can cause significant damage to forest trees and several other crops (Pertot *et al.*, 2008; Savazzini *et al.*, 2009).

The disease assumes importance in one or more of the following ways: which include the roots are killed and hence the trees die in one or more seasons; the base of trunk may be injured to such an extent that the tree may be blown over under the strain of a heavy crop of fruit; affected trees in bearing usually fail to mature their fruit, particularly in cases of severe infection; or the fruit matures poorly, is stunted and is of an inferior

quality; diseased trees often lack the normal amount of foliage; and affected plants make little or no growth (Skovsgaard *et al.*, 2010).

The disease remains undetected until symptomatic plants are observed, by which time *Armillaria* species may be widely spread both in soil and within the plant. *Armillaria* species forms rhizomorphs that can go deep into the soil, and mycelium remains protected, beneath the plant bark or inside dead wood, from the action of any control agent (Thomidis and Exadaktylou, 2012). Cultural methods such as removal of plant residues that may harbour the fungus and eradication of diseased plants are recommended for minimizing the risk of the disease, but complete elimination of the inoculum by this method is difficult in established crop stands Its success also depends on early and accurate diagnosis of the disease, which is difficult before the appearance of above ground symptoms. The limited access to the pathogen inside dead plant materials and its extensive rhizomorphs systems also limits the efficacy of chemical fumigants such as carbon disulphide (Otieno *et al.*, 2003). In addition, fumigation of infested soil is another method used as a preventive measure of this disease before establishing a new planting season (Adaskaveg *et al.*, 1999). However, Guillaumin (1988) noted that to be effective, the fumigants should be injected at least 60 cm deep in the soil but even this does not completely eradicate the fungus. Complete eradication of *Armillaria* sp. from an infested site by use of the above method is therefore difficult and alternative methods of destroying inocula fungus within plant materials in the soil are desirable.

Biological control (BC) of plant diseases is any means of controlling disease or reducing the amount or effect of pathogens that relies on biological mechanisms or organisms other than man (Hofte and Altier, 2010). The BC of plant diseases has received more consideration in the recent decades because of its efficacy against

fungicide-resistant pathogens in addition to reduced possibility of resistance development (Brimner and Boland, 2003; John *et al.*, 2010). Moreover, many research studies have shown that BC offers an environmentally friendly alternative to protect plants from soil borne pathogens (Yangui *et al.*, 2008). There is significant interest in finding alternatives to fungicides for suppression of soil borne pathogens (Roberts *et al.*, 2007) due to several negative effects, like development of pathogen resistance, hazards to humans, damage to non-target beneficial organisms, and environmental pollution (Brimner and Boland, 2003; Begum *et al.*, 2010). In addition, application of fungicides and fumigants are expensive and can be harmful to plants and their efficacy has been reduced by the appearance of microbial resistance (Sang *et al.*, 2008; Quagliotto *et al.*, 2009).

The antagonists are biological agents that reduce the population density or disease-producing activities of the pathogen and therefore use of antagonistic micro-organism for disease control is being studied (Jung *et al.*, 2003). Emerging strategies for plant disease control involve application of antagonistic micro-organisms alone or in combination (De Curtis *et al.*, 2010). Unfortunately, biological control agents (BCAs) applied alone are not likely to perform consistently against all pathogens or under different rhizosphere and / or soil environmental conditions (Roberts *et al.*, 2005). A combination of different antagonists is more likely to have a greater diversity of traits responsible for suppression of one or more pathogens resulting in improved control of pathogens (Postma *et al.*, 2009). The BC using microbial inoculants has proved to be a reliable component of integrated management of fungal diseases (Tchameni *et al.*, 2011). Among the microbial inoculants, AMF and members of the genus *Trichoderma* have emerged as promising groups of fungi that improve plant nutrition and health (Martínez-Medina *et al.*, 2011a).

Fungi of the genus *Trichoderma* are used extensively in the biocontrol of plant diseases (Wijesinghe *et al.*, 2011). They are common components of rhizosphere soil and have been reported to suppress a great number of plant diseases (Martínez-Medina *et al.*, 2011b). *Trichoderma* species have shown antagonistic activities towards a range of agriculturally devastating phytopathogenic microorganisms, including those within the genus *Fusarium*, *Phytophthora*, *Sclerotinia*, *Rhizoctonia* and *Pythium* (Beaulieu *et al.*, 2011). The AMF belongs to the phylum *Glomeromycota* and are key components of soil microbiota where they establish mutualistic symbioses with the majority of plants improving the nutritional status of their host and protecting it against several soil-borne plant pathogens (Martínez-Medina *et al.*, 2011b; Tian *et al.*, 2011; Veresoglou *et al.*, 2012). Alleviation of damage caused by soil-borne pathogens, such as *Phytophthora*, *Fusarium*, *Pythium*, *Rhizoctonia*, *Sclerotium* and *Verticillium* has been reported widely in mycorrhizal plants (Martínez-Medina *et al.*, 2011b).

Several reports have established that the interaction of these two groups of microorganisms may be beneficial for both plant growth and plant disease control. (Martínez-Medina *et al.*, 2011b). A synergistic effect of some saprophytic fungi on AMF spore germination and colonization has been confirmed. For example, it has been reported that some *Trichoderma* strains may influence AMF activity (Martínez-Medina *et al.*, 2009a). Although interactions between AMF and rhizobacteria have been extensively studied, interactions of AMF with saprophytic beneficial fungal species have received little attention (Chandanie *et al.*, 2009). Dual inoculations of AMF and *Trichoderma* might provide a higher level of protection and wider range of effectiveness by activating several different mechanisms. Limited studies has been done to evaluate the effectiveness of the above fungi to control *Armillaria* species in *D. torrida* plants.

Thus, the aim of this study was to evaluate the efficacy of application of different biocontrol agents: *Trichoderma* species and mycorrhizae, singly or in combination, for the control of *Armillaria* root rot in green house condition so as to contribute to a more suitable and environmentally acceptable alternative for sustainable agriculture and forestry.

Materials and methods

Source of fungal inoculants, potting medium and host plants

Armillaria species initially isolated from a severely infected *D. torrida* plant was kindly provided by Tea Research Foundation of Kenya. The species was isolated using *Armillaria* selective medium and maintained on malt extract agar (MEA) medium at room temperature. The inoculum of AMF which consisted of spores, hyphae, colonized root fragments and *Trichoderma* isolates were provided by Homegrown (K) Limited-Naivasha. In order to obtain fresh active cultures of *Trichoderma* isolates for *in-vitro* test, isolates were sub-cultured on MEA plates and incubated at 25°C for 7 days in the dark.

The dark brown loam soil collected from Sururu forest of Eastern Mau (2716 m a.s.l. 00°38.862 S and 036°01.467 E), was sieved (4 mm), mixed with river sand and compost manure (1:1:1) and sterilized by autoclaving for 1 h at 121°C twice, on two consecutive days (Toshihiro *et al.*, 2004). The *D. torrida* was used as the host plant and the seeds of these plants were collected from Mau forest complex.

Experimental design and biological treatments

The experiment was conducted. The experiment was conducted in a completely randomized design with three factors (AMF inoculation, *T. harzianum* inoculation and *Armillaria* species) to test the interaction between *T. asperellum* and AMF on fungal colonization, plant growth promotion and *Armillaria* species suppression in a

glasshouse at Biological Sciences department, Egerton University. (1) Control (c) (no addition of *Armillaria* species or biocontrol inoculum); (2) *Armillaria* species (A); (3) *T. asperellum* (T); (4) Arbuscular mycorrhizae fungi (M); (5) *T. asperellum* and Arbuscular mycorrhizae fungi (T + M); (6) *T. asperellum* and *Armillaria* species (T+A); (7) Arbuscular mycorrhizae fungi and *Armillaria* species (M+A); (8) *T. asperellum* and AMF and *Armillaria* species (T + M +A). The experiments were conducted in triplicate.

Inoculation of plants with fungal species

Inocula of mycorrhizal comprised 15 g of mycorrhizal inocula (spores, hyphae and infected root systems) or 15 g of autoclaved inoculum plus 10 ml of 15g inoculum filtrate through a 25µm filter to correct the potential differences in microbial communities between mycorrhizal and non-mycorrhizal pots (Wu and Zou, 2010). Inoculum of *T. asperellum* comprising of powder formulation was prepared according to manufactures instruction. Sterile water (100 mL) was added to the 10g of the formulation and mixed with a sterile stirring rod.

The resulting suspension was introduced to potted *D. torrida* seedlings. The inoculations of *T. asperellum* were done at 0, 30, 60, 90, 120 and 150 days from the beginning of the experiment in order to maintain sufficient populations of the antagonist in the soils and thus favour biological control, as suggested by Knudsen *et al.* (1991). *Armillaria* species inoculum was prepared by growing the culture on malt extract agar (MEA) and incubated at 25 °C for 14 days old.

Each plant was inoculated after every 30 days by placing four agar plugs cut from 14 days-olds MEA cultures of *Armillaria* species (Baumgartner *et al.*, 2010). The inoculum was introduced to the root zone of potted plants. The three fungal inocula, *Armillaria* species, and *T. asperellum* were applied singly or in combination according to the treatment.

Plant growth

Selected tree seeds were surface sterilized by immersing them in a 1% solution of sodium hypochlorite for 5 min, rinsed twice in double distilled sterile water (DDSW) and air dried them on sterile filter paper (Coskuntuna and Ozer, 2008). The seeds were placed in half full petri-dishes with water then incubated at 28° C in the dark for two days. Five pre-germinated seeds of *D. torrida* seedlings were each planted in pot filled with potting medium mixed with fungal inocula according to the treatment combination. The seedlings were thinned to one seedling per pot after three weeks. Final harvest was done after 28 weeks and the roots washed in DDSW.

Determination of colony forming units of T. asperellum on dombeya torrida rhizoplane

The estimation of colony forming units (CFUs) of *T. asperellum* in the rhizoplane were determined using an improved protocol used by Rosa and Herrera (2009). One gram fresh root tissue, previously disinfected in sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) solution for 6 min, was cut into pieces transferred into 100ml DDW in a test tubes containing then serially diluted, and 0.1 ml of each dilution was finally plated on fresh *Trichoderma* selective medium (TSM) (Elad *et al.*, 1981). The plates were incubated for 14 to 18 hours at 25°C in the dark in triplicate. The population counts of *T. asperellum* colonies on each Petri-dish were recorded, and data expressed as CFUs per gram fresh root.

Armillaria species assay

At the end of the experiments plants were assayed for viability of *Armillaria* species using a modified protocol used by Otieno *et al.* (2003a). One gram fresh root tissue, previously disinfected in NaOCl for 6 min, was cut into pieces and transferred to *Armillaria* semi-selective medium. Inoculated petri dishes were incubated at room temperature in the dark for at least 21 days in triplicate.

Measurement of plant parameters and data analysis

At the end of the experiment plant height, shoot and root fresh weights were measured the roots were separated from the soil by washing and fresh weights were measured. For all data (plant growth parameters, mycorrhizal root colonization), treatments were compared using one-way analysis of variances ($p < 0.05$) using Gen stat. the experiment was conducted three times and data from the repeated trials were pooled. The data was subjected to ANOVA and treatment means were compared by Fisher's least significant difference.

Results

Interaction between amf and T. asperellum under greenhouse conditions

Plant shoot and root fresh weight

Growth parameters of *D. torrida* seedlings grown in soils inoculated with AMF and *T. asperellum* were variably affected when examined after 28 weeks. Plants inoculated with *T. asperellum* alone had significantly increased shoot fresh weight compared to the control plants. Single inoculation of AMF did not significantly change shoot fresh weight compared with control plants. Plants co-inoculated with *T. asperellum* and AMF showed the highest fresh weights. Co-inoculation with AMF and *T. asperellum* significantly increased root and shoot fresh weights compared to *T. asperellum* alone or AMF alone (Table 1). Inoculations with *T. asperellum* only resulted in better root weight compared to inoculation with AMF. On the other hand, fresh shoots of plants inoculated with AMF were weightier than control plants. Although no significant changes in the shoot fresh weight due to inoculation with AMF, an increased shoot/root ratio was observed in AMF inoculated plants compared to control plants (Table 1). A significant interaction between the AMF and *T. asperellum* was observed regarding the shoot / root ratio. Combination of *T. asperellum* and AMF resulted in higher increases of root weight than shoot weight as illustrated by

the decrease in the shoot / root ratio. Moreover, smaller fresh shoot / root ratios were recorded in plants inoculated with *T. asperellum*.

Plant height

The other important parameters reflecting the seedling vigour of plants include the direct measurements of plant growth such as height. Although AMF inoculated plants had increased plant height, the difference was not significant

from the control. *T. asperellum* inoculants significantly increased the plant height compared to the AMF inoculated plants. Plant height was found to be enhanced by the combined inoculation of AMF and *T. asperellum* compared to individual inoculations. The highest plant height of 82.25 cm was recorded in treatment which received combined inoculation of the two of microorganisms (Table 1).

Table 1. The plant height, shoot and root fresh weight (g), and the shoot/root ratio of *D. torrida* plants inoculated with *T. asperellum* and/or AMF, 28 weeks after planting.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)	Shoot fresh weight (g/plant)	Root fresh weight (g/plant)	Shoot/root ratio
C	61.62ab	13.42a	3.963a	3.538c
A	61.75ab	13.50a	3.975a	3.538c
M	65.38 ab	13.56a	4.013a	3.550c
A+M	52.25a	15.66a	4.575a	3.725c
T	72.00bc	18.26ab	9.050b	2.038ab
A+TA	71.75bc	18.39ab	6.737ab	2.775bc
A+TA+M	74.62bc	21.54bc	14.663c	1.562a
M+TA	82.25c	23.82c	16.150c	1.562a

Data in the same column sharing a letter in common do not differ significantly (P<0.05) by the Fischer's least significant difference test

Treatments: A-*Armillaria* species; C-control; M-mycorrhizae; T-*Trichoderma* species

Root colonization

There were variations in root colonization of *D. torrida* seedlings grown in soils inoculated with AMF and *T. asperellum* when examined after 28 weeks (Table 2). Plants grown in soil inoculated with AMF alone were successfully colonized whereas non-inoculated plants remained non-mycorrhizal. Dual inoculation of *T. asperellum* and AMF significantly reduced the level of root colonisation by AMF (Table 2). Population density (CFU) of *T. asperellum* in the rhizosphere soil of combine inoculated plants (*T. asperellum*-AMF) was almost similar to that of plants inoculated with *T. asperellum* alone. The number of CFUs in the assays performed ranged between 39400 and 44000. There was no significant difference between the CFU of *T. asperellum* associated with roots of single and combine-inoculated plants (*T. asperellum*-AMF) 28 weeks after planting. No mycorrhizal colonization was recorded in control treatment (Table 2).

Table 2. The AMF root colonization and *T. asperellum* CFUs 28 weeks after planting and *Armillaria* root rot incidence.

Treatment	<i>T. asperellum</i> CFUs	AM root colonization	<i>Armillaria</i> root rot incidence
A	0.00 a	0.00a	0.00
C	0.00 a	0.00a	0.00
T	44.00b	0.00a	0.00
T+A	42.60b	0.00a	0.00
T+M+A	39.40b	19.40b	0.00
T+M	40.00b	21.80b	0.00
M	0.00 a	41.40c	0.00

Data in the same column sharing a letter in common do not differ significantly (P<0.05) by the Fischer's least significant difference test

Treatments: A-*Armillaria* species; C-control; M-mycorrhizae; T-*Trichoderma* species

Discussion

Interaction between amf and t. asperellum

This study presents the first assessment of AMF and *T. asperellum* to enhance growth and resistance of *D. torrida* against *Armillaria* species,

the causal agent of Armillaria root rot disease under greenhouse conditions. Differences that emerged from measurements of plant growth parameters following the inoculation of plants with *T. asperellum* and AMF provided a number of lines of evidence to show that microbial inoculations could improve growth of *D. torrida* seedlings. In this study, significant increases in plant height, root and shoot weights were observed after inoculation with *T. asperellum* and AMF, although these increases were not similar for all treatments. Microbial inoculants are promising components for integrated solutions to agro-environmental problems because inoculants possess the capacity to promote plant growth, enhance nutrient availability and uptake, and support the health of plants (Mader *et al.*, 2011). The smallest shoot/root ratios were obtained with the treatment involving the dual inoculation with *T. asperellum* and AMF, showing that the combined inoculation of *T. asperellum* and AMF was not essential for the promotion of plant growth. This may be explained by the different modes of action of *T. asperellum* and AMF and their interaction in dual inoculated *D. torrida* plants. The interaction between AMF and *T. harzianum* and its effect on plant growth may vary depending on the inherent characteristics of the AMF and the *T. harzianum* strain (Martínez-Medina *et al.* (2011_a)). Several reports have demonstrated that the interaction of these two groups of microorganisms may be beneficial for both plant growth and plant disease control (Martínez-Medina *et al.*, 2009).

Although saprophytic fungi have been reported to influence AMF colonization and host plant response, the effects of the saprophytic fungi on AMF formation differ depending on the inherent characteristic of both agents (Martínez-Medina *et al.*, 2011_a). AMF colonization levels of *D. torrida* seedlings were significantly reduced when dually inoculated with *T. asperellum*. This could be due to inhibition of AMF by *T. asperellum* through parasitism. As a biocontrol agent, the mechanism

of action of *T. asperellum* is known to be based on mycoparasitism (Mbarga *et al.*, 2012). It could, therefore, be possible for *T. asperellum* to have had a deleterious effect on the AMF as reported by Rousseau *et al.* (1996).

In the current investigations, inoculations with AMF and *T. asperellum* resulted in higher increases of root weight than shoot weight as illustrated by the decrease in the shoot/root ratio. The shoot/root ratio of a plant is a good indicator of plant stress, whereby the lower the shoot/root ratio, the more stressed the plant (Naseby *et al.*, 2000). The smallest shoot/root ratios were obtained with the treatment involving *T. asperellum* alone and the dual inoculation with *T. asperellum* and AMF, showing that the combined inoculation of *T. asperellum* and AMF was not essential for the promotion of plant growth. Similarly, root and shoot weights of soya beans were decreased by co-inoculation with *T. pseudokoningii* and *Gigaspora rosea* (Martínez *et al.*, 2004). Since the present experiment was conducted under controlled conditions with daily watering, a possible cause of stress could have been nutrient limitations and thus, a decrease in shoot/ root ratio could indicate such stress (Naseby *et al.*, 2000). Under these conditions, a larger increase of root weight is related to the expansion of the root system as a result of their search for more nutrients. While other reports indicate positive interactions following the combined inoculation of saprophytic fungal species and AMF (Srivastava *et al.*, 2010; Erman *et al.*, 2011), the reduced effectiveness of the combined use of the saprophytic fungus *T. asperellum* and the AMF in this study, suggests that the interactions of saprophytic fungi with AMF may differ depending on the AMF, the host plants and the species of the saprophytic fungus.

Conclusion

Dual inoculation of young *D. torrida* seedlings with the biocontrol agents *T. asperellum* and the AMF were found to have enhanced plant growth

compared to individual inoculations. However, negative interference between AMF and *T. asperellum* on root colonization has been demonstrated, showing their possible incompatibility to occupy the same rhizosphere.

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